

On the Adaptive Tracking Problem of Time-Varying Systems using the Congelation for Variables Method^{*}

Kaiwen Chen^{*} Alessandro Astolfi^{*,**}

^{*} *Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Imperial College London, London, SW7 2AZ, UK.*

^{**} *Dipartimento di Ingegneria Civile e Ingegneria Informatica, Università di Roma “Tor Vergata”, Rome, 00133, Italy.
E-mail: {kaiwen.chen16, a.astolfi}@imperial.ac.uk*

Abstract: This paper discusses the use of the so-called congelation of variables method in the reference tracking problem for a class of nonlinear systems with matched, time-varying, parametric uncertainty. It is shown that the tracking problem using the proposed framework can be decomposed into a zero-regulation problem and a disturbance rejection problem. To reduce the size of the disturbance term, a dynamical system with known input is incorporated into the parameter update law to generate a time-varying nominal parameter. To reject the remaining disturbance term, a sign-like function is exploited, which achieves an adjustable tracking performance in an average sense, while guaranteeing boundedness of all trajectories of the closed-loop system. The theory is illustrated by solving a path-tracking problem and it is shown that the proposed control scheme outperforms the classical scheme in the presence of time-varying parameters.

Keywords: Adaptive control, Time-varying systems, Lyapunov methods

1. INTRODUCTION

Adaptive control is a popular nonlinear control scheme which allows to cope with unknown parametric uncertainty, typically incurred by a changing plant or environment. Nevertheless, for most classical adaptive control schemes designed for constant-parameter systems (see, *e.g.*, Narendra and Annaswamy (1989); Krstic et al. (1995); Ioannou and Sun (1996); Astolfi et al. (2007)), the supporting proofs exploit the property that the parameters are constant or slowly varying in some senses. The main reason for this limitation is that the system parameter θ is used in the candidate Lyapunov functions. Thus when differentiating the candidate Lyapunov function, the time derivative of θ appears, depriving them of either the passivity or the \mathcal{L}_2 -stability property that holds in the constant-parameter scenarios and therefore making the stability proofs difficult.

Since the time derivative of θ is typically coupled with the parameter estimation error $\theta - \hat{\theta}$, if one can guarantee boundedness of the parameter estimates $\hat{\theta}$, the effects of slowly time-varying parameters can be viewed as the effects of bounded disturbances. To this end, several

attempts have been made to solve issues associated to the presence of time-varying parameters since the 1980s. Two widely used techniques are the *projection operation* (see, *e.g.*, Goodwin and Mayne (1987)) and the *switching σ -modification* (see, *e.g.*, Ioannou and Tsakalis (1986)). These modifications guarantee boundedness of the parameter estimation error, and only add non-positive terms to the Lyapunov analysis, which does not undermine the results guaranteed by the unmodified update law. Exploiting these modified update laws, if the parameter variations are slow in some senses, bounded tracking error can be achieved (see, *e.g.*, Tsakalis and Ioannou (1987); Middleton and Goodwin (1988); Wang et al. (2009)), and if the rates of parameter variations satisfy some integrability conditions, asymptotic tracking can be achieved (see, *e.g.*, Marino and Tomei (1999, 2003)). An unresolved issue is that the candidate Lyapunov function still contains the time-varying parameters, and as a result, fast varying parameters can reduce performance, as their time derivatives are present in the analysis.

In other works, instead of using the classical controller structure developed in the spirit of the *certainty-equivalence principle*, a high-gain design to dominate the parametric uncertainties is adopted. As the parameters of the high-gain controller are constant, it only remains to design an update law for the estimates of these parameters, using classical adaptive control techniques. These methods exploit either dynamically updated control gains (see *e.g.* Lin and Qian (2002); Wang and Guo (2017)), or sign-function-like “switching” terms multiplied by dynamically updated gains (see, *e.g.*, Huang et al. (2018); Zhang et al. (2019); Li (2022)). These methods can guarantee

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bounded tracking error if using continuously “switching” terms. Asymptotic results can be achieved by making the “switching” terms discontinuous or “asymptotically discontinuous”, but in this case, the classical concerns about discontinuous control law arise, such as “chattering” and lack of differentiability for recursive design, which undermines the significance of the asymptotic results¹.

Aside from the robustness issues, the high-gain schemes are solely designed to dominate the parametric uncertainties, whereas do not contain “estimates” that can be directly related to the system parameters. As a result, these designs cannot be parametrized by some metric, such as the amplitude or the rate, of parameter variations, which can transform the controller back to its classical counterpart when that metric goes to 0. In this sense they do not possess the “adaptive” property. The so-called *congelation of variables* method in Chen and Astolfi (2018, 2021a,b), however, can cope with time-varying parameters and retain the “adaptive” property at the same time. The general idea is to divide the original problem into an adaptive control design problem coping with the constant unknown parameters and a robust control design problem coping with the time-varying perturbations. This method does not require slow parameter variations and possesses the property that when the parameters are constant, the controller reduces to the associated classical controller. However, these results are limited to the solution of the set-point regulation problem, and the set-point has to be selected such that the regressor evaluated at the set-point vanishes (the set-point, after a change of coordinates, can be set to 0, hence the associated problem is also called zero-regulation problem). The original version of the method is not directly applicable to reference tracking problems. The aim of this paper is to remove such a restriction.

Fig. 1. Graphical illustration of the role of Θ_0 , $\ell_\theta(t)$, $\Delta_\theta(t)$, and δ_{Δ_θ} .

Notation. This paper uses standard notation unless stated otherwise. For an n -dimensional vector $v \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $|v|$ denotes the Euclidean 2-norm; $|v|_M \triangleq \sqrt{v^\top M v}$, $M = M^\top \succ 0$, denotes the weighted 2-norm with weight M . The vector e_i , $1 \leq i \leq n$, denotes the i th unit vector of \mathbb{R}^n . For an $n \times m$ matrix M , $(M)_i$ denotes the i th column; $(M)_{ij}$ denotes the i th element on the j th column; $\text{tr}(M)$ denotes the trace; and $|M|_F \triangleq \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m (M)_{ij}^2}$ denotes the

¹ It is worth noting that the drawbacks of using discontinuous control laws can be alleviated, though not overcome, by the second-order sliding-mode control techniques exploited by Patil et al. (2022).

Frobenius norm. For $M = M^\top \succeq 0$, $\lambda_{\min}(M)$ denotes the smallest eigenvalue of M (and similarly for λ_{\max}). I and S denote the identity matrix and the upper-shift matrix, respectively. For an n -dimensional time-varying signal $s : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, the image of which is contained in a compact set \mathcal{S} , $\Delta_s : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes the deviation of s from a reference value $\ell_s(t)$, i.e. $\Delta_s(t) \triangleq s(t) - \ell_s(t)$; and $\delta_s \in \mathbb{R}$ denotes the supremum of the 2-norm of s , i.e. $\delta_s \triangleq \sup_{t \geq 0} |s(t)| \geq 0$. A *projection operator*² for $\tau \in \mathbb{R}^q$, parametrized by $\hat{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^q$ and $\Gamma = \Gamma^\top \succ 0$, is denoted by $\text{proj}(\hat{\theta}, \Gamma, \tau)$. \diamond

In this paper the vector of unknown time-varying system parameters $\theta : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^q$ may verify one of the assumptions below.

Assumption 1. The parameter θ is piecewise continuous and $\theta(t) \in \Theta_0 + \ell_\theta(t)$, for all $t \geq 0$, where Θ_0 is a compact set and ℓ_θ is bounded. The radius of the circumscribed ball of Θ_0 , i.e. δ_{Δ_θ} , is assumed to be known, while $\ell_\theta(t)$ can be unknown (see Fig. 1). \diamond

The reference signal $r(t)$ satisfies the assumption below.

Assumption 2. The function $r : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is n th-order differentiable. The derivatives of r and itself, i.e. $r^{(i)}$, $i = 0, \dots, n$, are known. \diamond

2. FROM ZERO-REGULATION TO TRACKING

It is beneficial to understand how the tracking problem is related to and different from the zero-regulation problem discussed in Chen and Astolfi (2021a). To this end, consider the scalar nonlinear system

$$\dot{x} = \phi^\top(x)\theta + u, \quad (1)$$

where $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the system state; $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the input; $\phi : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^q$ is a smooth mapping, with its value $\phi(x)$ called the regressor; and $\theta(t) \in \mathbb{R}^q$ is a time-varying parameter. The objective of the reference tracking problem is to let the state x tracks a time-varying reference signal r . We consider two cases of reference tracking via the tracking error $z(t) \triangleq x(t) - r(t)$. In the first case $\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} z(t) = 0$, and this case is called asymptotic tracking. In the other case, asymptotic tracking cannot be achieved using continuous control law, and one may seek a weaker property (Tao, 2003, Definition 5.1), that is, for any $t_2 > t_1 \geq 0$, $\int_{t_1}^{t_2} z^2(t) dt \leq c_0 + c_1(t_2 - t_1)$, for some positive constants c_0 and c_1 . The second case can be understood as tracking with a bounded error in an average sense, specified by c_1 . Intuitively, if c_1 can be adjusted close to 0 by tuning some controller parameters, the tracking performance should be comparable to that achievable with asymptotic tracking.

Remark 1. The regressor $\phi(x)$ can be re-written as

² In this paper, we use the definition in (Krstic et al., 1995, Appendix E) for the *projection operator*. Briefly, this is an operator that projects the unmodified parameter update vector τ back to a prescribed convex set Π when $\hat{\theta}$ reaches the boundary of Π , such that Π is forward invariant with respect to the solutions of $\dot{\hat{\theta}} = \text{proj}(\hat{\theta}, \Gamma, \tau)$. Typically, one can select $\Pi \supset \Theta_0$, where Θ_0 is the nominal set in which the true parameter θ should stay. Then, for $\theta \in \Theta_0$, the inequality $-(\theta - \hat{\theta})^\top \Gamma^{-1} \text{proj}(\hat{\theta}, \tau) \leq -(\theta - \hat{\theta})^\top \Gamma^{-1} \tau$ holds.

$$\phi(x) = \phi(z+r) = \phi(r) + \bar{\phi}(z,r)z, \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{\phi}(z,r) : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^q$ is a smooth mapping. This is a direct result of smoothness of ϕ and Hadamard's lemma (see Hadamard (1903), for the original formulation, or Nestruev (2020), for a modern version). Moreover, according to (Nestruev, 2020, Lemma 2.8), $\bar{\phi}$, or in the case in which x, z, r are vectors satisfying $x = z+r$, its matrix counterpart, $\bar{\Phi}$, can be selected as $\bar{\Phi}(z,r) = \int_0^1 \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x}|_{x=r+zs} ds$, such that $\phi(x) = \phi(r) + \bar{\Phi}(z,r)z$. \diamond

To discuss the tracking problem, we rewrite the system dynamics in terms of the error variable, yielding

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z} &= \dot{x} - \dot{r} = \phi^\top(x)\theta + u - \dot{r} \\ &= \phi^\top(x)\ell_\theta + \bar{\phi}^\top(z,r)\Delta_\theta z + \phi^\top(r)\Delta_\theta - \dot{r} + u, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta_\theta(t) \triangleq \theta(t) - \ell_\theta(t)$ is the time-varying perturbation with respect to the *congealed* parameter ℓ_θ .

Remark 2. The *congealed* parameter ℓ_θ is not necessarily constant. The effect of using a time-varying ℓ_θ has been briefly discussed in Remark 5 of Chen and Astolfi (2021a) but has not been exploited in the literature. \diamond

To explain how to cope with each term in (3), we separately consider three cases as follows: 1) the *reference regressor* $\phi(r(t))$ is vanishing; 2) the parameter $\theta(t)$ is generated by a known dynamical system (the parameter model) with a known input; 3) $\theta(t)$ is composed of a component generated by a known model and a bounded unknown component.

In the first case, we assume that the following condition holds.

Assumption 3. The reference signal r and the regressor ϕ are such that $\int_0^{+\infty} |\phi(r(t))|^2 dt \leq \mu < +\infty$, where μ is a positive constant. \diamond

Due to smoothness of r and ϕ , Assumption 3 indicates that $\phi(r)$, the regressor evaluated along the reference (called the *reference regressor*), vanishes to 0 asymptotically, by Barbalat's lemma. A special case that results in a vanishing *reference regressor* in Assumption 3 is the zero-regulation problem, in which $r(t) = 0$, for all $t \geq 0$, and $\phi(0) = 0$. This special case has been discussed in Chen and Astolfi (2021a). In fact, the scheme used there can be exploited with modifications to solve the tracking problem under Assumption 3.

Proposition 1. Consider the system (1), with the parameter vector θ satisfying Assumption 1 and the reference r satisfying Assumption 2, and the adaptive controller described by

$$\dot{\hat{\theta}} = \text{proj}(\hat{\theta}, \gamma_\theta, \gamma_\theta \phi(x)z), \quad (4)$$

$$u = -(\bar{k}_1 + \bar{k}_2 |\bar{\phi}(z,r)|^2)z - \phi^\top(x)\hat{\theta} + \dot{r}, \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{k}_1 \triangleq k_1 + \frac{\delta_{\Delta_\theta}}{\epsilon_{\Delta_\theta}}$, $\bar{k}_2 \triangleq \frac{\epsilon_{\Delta_\theta} \delta_{\Delta_\theta}}{2}$, with positive constants $\gamma_\theta, k_1, \epsilon_{\Delta_\theta}$. Then, all trajectories of the closed-loop system are bounded. Furthermore, if Assumption 3 holds, $\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} z(t) = 0$. \diamond

Proof. Consider the Lyapunov function candidate $V(z, \hat{\theta}) = \frac{1}{2}z^2 + \frac{1}{2\gamma_\theta}|\ell_\theta - \hat{\theta}|^2$. Considering a constant ℓ_θ and

taking the time derivative of V along the trajectories of the closed-loop system yields $\dot{V} = -(\bar{k}_1 + \bar{k}_2 |\bar{\phi}(z,r)|^2)z^2 + \bar{\phi}^\top(z,r)\Delta_\theta z^2 + \phi^\top(r)\Delta_\theta z + (\ell_\theta - \hat{\theta})^\top(\phi(x)z - \gamma_\theta^{-1}\dot{\hat{\theta}})$. Noting that the *projection operator* guarantees that $-(\ell_\theta - \hat{\theta})^\top \gamma_\theta^{-1} \text{proj}(\hat{\theta}, \gamma_\theta, \gamma_\theta \phi(x)z) \leq -(\ell_\theta - \hat{\theta})^\top \phi(x)z$, yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V} &\leq -(\bar{k}_1 + \bar{k}_2 |\bar{\phi}(z,r)|^2)z^2 + \frac{\epsilon_{\Delta_\theta} \delta_{\Delta_\theta}}{2} |\phi(r)|^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{\delta_{\Delta_\theta}}{2\epsilon_{\Delta_\theta}} z^2 + \frac{\delta_{\Delta_\theta}}{2\epsilon_{\Delta_\theta}} z^2 + \frac{\epsilon_{\Delta_\theta} \delta_{\Delta_\theta}}{2} |\bar{\phi}(z,r)|^2 z^2 \\ &= -k_1 z^2 + \frac{\epsilon_{\Delta_\theta} \delta_{\Delta_\theta}}{2} |\phi(r)|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Since $\hat{\theta}$ is bounded, due to the *projection*, and so is the term $\frac{\epsilon_{\Delta_\theta} \delta_{\Delta_\theta}}{2} |\phi(r)|^2$, due to Assumption 2 and smoothness of ϕ , one can conclude that z is also bounded from (6). This means that x is also bounded and proves boundedness of all trajectories of the closed-loop system.

To conclude the convergence property, integrating both sides of (6) yields (with a slight abuse of notation in the argument of V) $V(t)|_0^{+\infty} \leq \int_0^{+\infty} -k_1 z^2 + \frac{\epsilon_{\Delta_\theta} \delta_{\Delta_\theta}}{2} |\phi(r)|^2 dt$, and by Assumption 3 one obtains that $0 \leq \int_0^{+\infty} k_1 z^2 dt \leq \frac{\mu \epsilon_{\Delta_\theta} \delta_{\Delta_\theta}}{2} + V(t)|_{+\infty}^0 < +\infty$. The integral term $\int_0^T k_1 z^2 dt$ is monotonically increasing in T and bounded, and therefore its limit at $T \rightarrow +\infty$ exists. Since both z and \dot{z} are bounded, one can conclude that $\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} z(t) = 0$ by invoking Barbalat's lemma. \square

Remark 3. Compared with the results in Chen and Astolfi (2021a), the *projection operator* (or similar robust adaptive law modifications, e.g. the *switching σ -modification* Ioannou and Tsakalis (1986)) is needed for establishing boundedness for closed-loop trajectories. However, the use of *projection* is not to turn the $\dot{\theta}$ -related terms into a bounded disturbance, like in many other works that directly include θ instead of ℓ_θ into the Lyapunov function candidate. \diamond

Remark 4. In the constant parameter case, that is, when $\ell_\theta = \theta$ and $\delta_{\Delta_\theta} = 0$, the adaptive control law (5) reduces to the classical controller which does not contain nonlinear damping terms. \diamond

3. UNKNOWN PARAMETERS GENERATED BY A KNOWN MODEL

In this section we do not require a specific reference signal to let Assumption 3 hold and do not exploit a constant *congealed* parameter vector ℓ_θ . Instead, we consider a time-varying $\ell_\theta(t) \in \mathbb{R}^q$, the dynamics of which can be described by

$$\dot{\varsigma} = F\varsigma + Gv, \quad \ell_\theta = H\varsigma + Lv, \quad (7)$$

where $\varsigma(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\varsigma}$ is a new state vector. F, G, H, L are known matrices with compatible dimensions, and $v(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{m_\varsigma}$ is a bounded known signal. Furthermore, F is selected in a way that there exist $X = X^\top \succ 0$ and $Y = Y^\top \succeq 0$ such that $F^\top X + XF + Y = 0$. Moreover, v is selected so that ς is bounded for all $t \geq 0$.

Remark 5. Compared to using a constant ℓ_θ , considering a time-varying ℓ_θ generated by (7) has the following

advantages: 1) if some partial knowledge of the frequency of the system parameter θ is available, one can incorporate such knowledge into F ; 2) if the system parameter has a known component that can be expressed as a filtered known signal v , this knowledge of v can also be exploited by (7). These features help to reduce the perturbation Δ and therefore δ_{Δ_θ} , which results in a less conservative design. A similar method of exploiting a parameter model other than $\dot{\theta} = 0$, has been considered in Freeman and Kokotovic (1996), though the counterpart of the parameter model therein does not have an external input and is referred to as “unmeasured state” dynamics. \diamond

To simplify the discussion, we first consider a case in which the unknown parameter is generated by a known system with a known input but with an unknown initial condition.

Assumption 4. The system parameter vector $\theta(t) \in \mathbb{R}^q$ is generated by the system

$$\dot{\sigma} = F\sigma + Gv, \quad \theta = H\sigma + Lv, \quad (8)$$

with an unknown initial condition $\sigma(0) = \sigma_0$. \diamond

Proposition 2. Consider the system (1), with the parameter vector θ satisfying Assumption 4, the reference signal r satisfying Assumption 2, the dynamic parameter update law described by the equations

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{\zeta}} &= F\hat{\zeta} + Gv + \Gamma H^\top \phi(x)z, \\ \dot{\hat{\theta}} &= H\hat{\zeta} + Lv, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

and the control law

$$u = -kz - \phi^\top(x)\hat{\theta} + \dot{r}, \quad (10)$$

where $\Gamma \triangleq X^{-1}$ and k is a positive constant. Then, all trajectories of the closed-loop system are bounded and $\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} z(t) = 0$. \diamond

Proof. First, let ς be the solution of (7) with the initial condition $\varsigma(0) = \sigma_0$, which guarantees, under Assumption 4, that $\varsigma(t) = \sigma(t)$, $\ell_\theta(t) = \theta(t)$, and therefore $\Delta_\theta(t) = 0$ in (3), for all $t \geq 0$. Consider now the function $V(z, \varsigma - \hat{\zeta}) = \frac{1}{2}z^2 + \frac{1}{2}|\varsigma - \hat{\zeta}|_X^2$. Differentiating V along the trajectories of the closed-loop system yields $\dot{V} = -kz^2 + z\phi^\top(\ell_\theta - H\hat{\zeta} - Lv) + \frac{1}{2}|\varsigma - \hat{\zeta}|_{F^\top X + XF}^2 - (\varsigma - \hat{\zeta})^\top H^\top \phi z \leq -kz^2 - \frac{1}{2}|\varsigma - \hat{\zeta}|_Y^2 + z\phi^\top H(\varsigma - \hat{\zeta}) - (\varsigma - \hat{\zeta})^\top H^\top \phi z = -kx^2 - \frac{1}{2}|\varsigma - \hat{\zeta}|_Y^2 \leq -kx^2 \leq 0$. From this we can conclude that z and $\varsigma - \hat{\zeta}$ are bounded. Then, boundedness of r and ς implies that x and $\hat{\zeta}$ are also bounded. This proves boundedness of trajectories of the closed-loop system. To conclude convergence, noting that both z and \dot{z} are bounded, and using an invariance-like argument based on Barbalat’s lemma, one can prove that $\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} z(t) = 0$ and the proof is complete. \square

4. DESIGN WITH PARTIALLY KNOWN PARAMETER MODELS

In what follows we combine the tools exploited in the previous sections: the control law with nonlinear damping and the parameter update law with model information, together with some disturbance rejection techniques to be discussed, to deal with the case in which the parameter model is not fully available. To do this, consider the system with *matched* parametric uncertainty, namely

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= x_2, \\ &\vdots \\ \dot{x}_{n-1} &= x_n, \\ \dot{x}_n &= \phi^\top(x)\theta + u, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $x(t) \triangleq [x_1(t), \dots, x_n(t)]^\top$ is the state vector that can be measured, $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the control input, and ϕ is the regressor of matched parametric uncertainty, the same as the ϕ defined for the scalar system (1). The objective is to let x_1 track r . To this end, we apply the change of coordinates $z_i \triangleq x_i - r^{(i-1)}$, for $i = 1, \dots, n$, which yields the dynamics in the error coordinates,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z}_1 &= z_2, \\ &\vdots \\ \dot{z}_{n-1} &= z_n, \\ \dot{z}_n &= \phi^\top(x) - r^{(n)} + u, \\ &= \phi^\top(x)\ell_\theta + z^\top \bar{\Phi}^\top(z, \bar{r})\Delta_\theta - d - r^{(n)} + u, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\bar{\Phi} : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^{n-1} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{q \times n}$ is a smooth mapping such that $\phi(x) = \phi(r) + \bar{\Phi}(z, \bar{r})z$, as in Remark 1; $\bar{r} \triangleq [r, \dot{r}, \dots, r^{(n-1)}]^\top$; and $d \triangleq \phi^\top(r)\Delta_\theta$ is treated as a bounded disturbance due to Assumptions 1 and 2.

In what follows, we neither require $\phi(r)$ to be vanishing (as in Assumption 3) nor require ℓ_θ to match θ , *i.e.* $\Delta_\theta(t) = 0$ for all $t \geq 0$ (as in Assumption 4). Since d is separated as a *matched* disturbance, it can be rejected or at least attenuated. A common technique to do this is to exploit a sliding-mode-like term, for example, a class of sigmoid functions $\text{sgm}(\cdot, \varepsilon)$, parametrized by a constant $\varepsilon > 0$. When ε approaches 0, $\text{sgm}(\cdot, \varepsilon)$ approaches the sign function $\text{sgn}(\cdot)$. The property of $\text{sgm}(\cdot, \varepsilon)$ to be exploited is the inequality

$$|x| - x\text{sgm}(x, \varepsilon) \leq \rho(\varepsilon), \quad (13)$$

where $\rho(\cdot)$ is a class- \mathcal{K} function. An example of such a function is

$$\text{sgm}(x, \varepsilon) = \frac{x}{\sqrt{x^2 + \varepsilon^2}}, \quad (14)$$

for which the inequality $|x| - x \frac{x}{\sqrt{x^2 + \varepsilon^2}} = \frac{|x|}{\sqrt{x^2 + \varepsilon^2}} (\sqrt{x^2 + \varepsilon^2} - |x|) \leq \varepsilon$ holds.

Consider now the parameter update law

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{\zeta}} &= F\hat{\zeta} + Gv + \text{proj}(\hat{\zeta}, \Gamma, H^\top \phi(x)e_n^\top Pz), \\ \dot{\hat{\theta}} &= H\hat{\zeta} + Lv, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

and the control law

$$\begin{aligned} u &= -k^\top z - \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon_{\Delta_\theta} \delta_{\Delta_\theta} |\bar{\Phi}(z, \bar{r})|_{\mathbb{F}}^2 e_n^\top Pz \\ &\quad - \phi^\top(x)\hat{\theta} - \beta \text{sgm}(e_n^\top Pz, \varepsilon) + r^{(n)}, \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $\beta \geq \delta_a$; $\varepsilon > 0$; $k \triangleq \frac{1}{2}\gamma^{-1}Pe_n$; and $P = P^\top \succ 0$ is such that the algebraic Riccati equation holds

$$S^\top P + PS - \gamma^{-1}Pe_n e_n^\top P + \left(Q + \frac{\delta_{\Delta_\theta}}{\varepsilon_{\Delta_\theta}} I \right) = 0 \quad (17)$$

with $\gamma > 0$ and $Q = Q^\top \succ 0$.

Theorem 1. Consider the system (11), with θ satisfying Assumption 1, r satisfying Assumption 2, and the adaptive controller described by (16). Then, all trajectories of the closed-loop system are bounded, and the tracking error z_1 , for any $t_2 > t_1 \geq 0$ satisfies the condition $\int_{t_1}^{t_2} z_1^2(t) dt \leq c_0 + c_1(t_2 - t_1)$, for some positive constants c_0 and c_1 . \diamond

Proof. Consider the function $V_z(z) \triangleq |z|_P^2$ and differentiate it along the trajectories of the closed-loop system. This yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_z &= |z|_{S^\top P + PS}^2 - \gamma^{-1} (e_n^\top Pz)^2 + 2z^\top P e_n \phi^\top (H\zeta - \hat{\theta}) \\ &\quad - \epsilon_{\Delta_\theta} \delta_{\Delta_\theta} |\bar{\Phi}|_F^2 (e_n^\top Pz)^2 + 2z^\top P e_n \Delta_\theta^\top \bar{\Phi} z \\ &\quad - 2z^\top P e_n \beta \text{sgm}(e_n^\top Pz) - 2z^\top P e_n d \\ &\leq -|z|_Q^2 - 2(|e_n^\top Pz|(\beta - \delta_d) - \beta\rho(\varepsilon)) \\ &\quad + 2z^\top P e_n \phi^\top H(\zeta - \hat{\zeta}) \\ &\leq -|z|_Q^2 + 2z^\top P e_n \phi^\top H(\zeta - \hat{\zeta}) + 2\beta\rho(\varepsilon). \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Consider now the function $V_\zeta(\zeta - \hat{\zeta}) \triangleq |\zeta - \hat{\zeta}|_X^2$. Taking its time derivative along the trajectories of the *congealed* parameter and parameter update law dynamics yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_\zeta &= 2(\zeta - \hat{\zeta})^\top X(F(\zeta - \hat{\zeta}) - \text{proj}(\hat{\zeta}, \Gamma, H^\top \phi e_n^\top Pz)) \\ &= |\zeta - \hat{\zeta}|_{F^\top X + XF}^2 \\ &\quad - 2(\zeta - \hat{\zeta})^\top \Gamma^{-1} \text{proj}(\hat{\zeta}, \Gamma, H^\top \phi e_n^\top Pz). \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Note that $(\zeta - \hat{\zeta})^\top \Gamma^{-1} \text{proj}(\hat{\zeta}, \Gamma, H^\top \phi e_n^\top Pz) \leq (\zeta - \hat{\zeta})^\top H^\top \phi e_n^\top Pz$. This yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_\zeta &\leq |\zeta - \hat{\zeta}|_{F^\top X + XF}^2 - 2(\zeta - \hat{\zeta})^\top H^\top \phi e_n^\top Pz \\ &\leq -2(\zeta - \hat{\zeta})^\top H^\top \phi e_n^\top Pz. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Consider now the function $V(z, \zeta - \hat{\zeta}) \triangleq V_z(z) + V_\zeta(\zeta - \hat{\zeta})$. The time derivative of V along the trajectories of the closed-loop system is

$$\dot{V} = \dot{V}_z + \dot{V}_\zeta \leq -|z|_Q^2 + 2\beta\rho(\varepsilon). \quad (21)$$

Exploiting the property of the *projection* operator, $\hat{\zeta}$ is bounded and therefore by (21), z is also bounded. Moreover, integrating both sides of (21) yields

$$V(t) \Big|_{t_1}^{t_2} \leq - \int_{t_1}^{t_2} |z(t)|_Q^2 dt + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} 2\beta\rho(\varepsilon) dt. \quad (22)$$

Re-arranging, yields $\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \lambda_{\min}(Q) |z(t)|^2 dt \leq \sup_{t \geq 0} V(t) + 2\beta\rho(\varepsilon)(t_2 - t_1)$ and therefore $\int_{t_1}^{t_2} z_1^2(t) dt \leq \int_{t_1}^{t_2} |z(t)|^2 dt \leq c_0 + c_1(t_2 - t_1)$, where $c_0 \triangleq \frac{\sup_{t \geq 0} V(t)}{\lambda_{\min}(Q)}$, $c_1 \triangleq \frac{2\beta\rho(\varepsilon)}{\lambda_{\min}(Q)}$. This completes the proof. \square

Remark 6. As $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, $\rho(\varepsilon) \rightarrow 0$, and $c_2 \rightarrow 0$. In this case, z_1 is converging to 0 in an average sense. However, the closer ε is to 0, the closer the $\text{sgm}(\cdot, \varepsilon)$ term is to a discontinuous sign function, in which case the chattering issue of the sliding-mode-type methods emerges. \diamond

Remark 7. From the “disturbance” term $d = \phi^\top(r)\Delta_\theta$ one can see that the proposed scheme does not require slow parameter variations, as d does not depend on $\dot{\theta}$ -terms. This indicates that the proposed scheme is suitable for systems with fast-varying parameters. \diamond

5. SIMULATION

In this section a practical example is provided to show how to implement the proposed adaptive scheme. Consider the path-tracking problem for dual-wheel vehicles (Ioannou and Fidan, 2006, Section 8.8). The kinematic model for this problem can be described by the equations

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{y} &= V_c \sin \psi, \\ \dot{\psi} &= -\frac{\kappa}{1 - \kappa y} V_c \cos \psi + \omega, \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where y is the lateral deviation from the path; ψ is the orientation deviation from the angle of the path tangent, at the current location; V_c is the speed of the centre of the dual-wheel axle; κ is the curvature of the path at the current location; and ω is the angular rate of the vehicle, which is used as control input.

To simplify the problem, we consider the case in which $\psi \ll 1$ and $y \ll 1/\kappa \triangleq R$, where R is the radius of curvature. These allow the approximations that $\sin \psi \approx \psi$ and $\frac{1}{1 - \kappa y} \approx 1 + \kappa y$. In addition, for dual-wheel vehicles using a differential drive, the forward speed can be kept constant while the vehicle is making a turn, and therefore V_c is treated as a known constant. Then, the system can be re-written using the equations

$$x_1 = x_2, \quad x_2 = \phi^\top(x)\theta + u, \quad (24)$$

where $x_1 \triangleq y$; $x_2 \triangleq V_c \psi$; $u \triangleq V_c \omega$; $\theta \triangleq [-\kappa V_c^2, -\kappa^2 V_c^2]^\top$; $\phi(x) \triangleq [\cos(x_2/V_c), x_1 \cos(x_2/V_c)]^\top$. The task is to let x_1 track a time-varying signal $r = 0.1 \sin t$ at $V_c = 1$ m/s. As the vehicle moves along the curved path, κ is naturally a time-varying parameter. Moreover, if the curvature of the route is periodic with respect to the distance travelled, it is also periodic with respect to time since the vehicle travels at a constant speed. Assume that the curvature satisfies

$$\kappa(t) = \sin t + 0.2 \sin 5t. \quad (25)$$

The designer only knows that κ contains a 1 rad/s sinusoidal component and an unmodelled component with its absolute value bounded by 0.2, whereas does not know the amplitude of the 1 rad/s component or the parameter model of the 5 rad/s component. This verifies Assumption 1, since “ $\sin t$ ” and “ $0.2 \sin 5t$ ” are characterized by $\ell_\theta(t)$ and $\Delta_\theta(t)$, respectively. To this end, consider the controller in (15) and (16), with $F = \text{diag}\left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, 0, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 2 \\ -2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, 0\right)$, $H = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$, and G, L zero matrices. Note that the diagonal 0-terms in F is to compensate for constant biases and the 2 rad/s oscillator is to compensate for the κ^2 term (the frequency of a sinusoidal function doubles after squared). The other controller parameters are set to $Q = 5I$, $\gamma = 1$, $\epsilon_{\Delta_\theta} = 1$, $\delta_{\Delta_\theta} = 0.2$, $\beta = 0.2$. The sigmoid function used for the control law is as in (14) with $\varepsilon = 0.01$. A classical adaptive controller designed for time-invariant systems is used for comparison, which does not contain the strengthened nonlinear damping term and the sigmoid term in (16), and does not incorporate oscillators in F .

Simulations are run on the original nonlinear model (23) and the results are plotted in Fig. 2. These results show that the proposed controller has higher tracking accuracy in steady state, and incurs fewer oscillations in steering in the transient stage.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have discussed how to extend the *congealation of variables* method to reference tracking problems. It has been shown that the adaptive tracking problem using the *congealation of variables* framework can be viewed as a superposition of the zero-regulation problem and a disturbance rejection problem, that is, the zero-regulation problem is a special case in which the disturbance term is vanishing. As the disturbance is related to the amplitude

Fig. 2. Time histories of the tracking error z and the control input u , controlled by different controllers.

of the deviation between the *congealed* parameter and the true parameter, a nominal system that generates a time-varying *congealed* parameter is incorporated into the design. Finally, a smooth, saturated, parametrized high-gain term is introduced into the control law to cope with the remaining disturbance term. The closed-loop trajectories are guaranteed to be bounded and the tracking performance is adjustable. A path-tracking problem has been studied and it has shown that the proposed scheme has superior tracking performance compared to that of the classical scheme designed for time-invariant systems.

The relation between the proposed scheme and a standard internal-model-based output regulation scheme is to be further studied in future work to generalize the current results.

REFERENCES

- Astolfi, A., Karagiannis, D., and Ortega, R. (2007). *Nonlinear and Adaptive Control with Applications*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Chen, K. and Astolfi, A. (2018). I&I adaptive control for systems with varying parameters. In *Proc. 57th IEEE Conf. Decis. and Control*, 2205–2210. IEEE.
- Chen, K. and Astolfi, A. (2021a). Adaptive control for systems with time-varying parameters. *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, 66(5), 1986–2001.
- Chen, K. and Astolfi, A. (2021b). Identification-based adaptive control for systems with time-varying parameters. In *Proc. 60th IEEE Conf. Decis. and Control*, 1083–1088. IEEE.
- Freeman, R.A. and Kokotovic, P.V. (1996). Tracking controllers for systems linear in the unmeasured states.

- Automatica*, 32(5), 735–746.
- Goodwin, G.C. and Mayne, D.Q. (1987). A parameter estimation perspective of continuous time model reference adaptive control. *Automatica*, 23(1), 57–70.
- Hadamard, J. (1903). *Lessons on Wave Propagation and the Equations of Hydrodynamics*. A. Hermann (in French).
- Huang, J., Wang, W., Wen, C., and Zhou, J. (2018). Adaptive control of a class of strict-feedback time-varying nonlinear systems with unknown control coefficients. *Automatica*, 93, 98–105.
- Ioannou, P. and Tsakalis, K. (1986). A robust direct adaptive controller. *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, 31(11), 1033–1043.
- Ioannou, P. and Fidan, B. (2006). *Adaptive Control Tutorial*. SIAM.
- Ioannou, P.A. and Sun, J. (1996). *Robust Adaptive Control*. PTR Prentice-Hall Upper Saddle River, NJ.
- Krstic, M., Kokotovic, P.V., and Kanellakopoulos, I. (1995). *Nonlinear and Adaptive Control Design*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc, New York, NY, USA, 1st edition.
- Li, Y.X. (2022). Command filter adaptive asymptotic tracking of uncertain nonlinear systems with time-varying parameters and disturbances. *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, 67(6), 2973–2980.
- Lin, W. and Qian, C. (2002). Adaptive control of nonlinearly parameterized systems: the smooth feedback case. *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, 47(8), 1249–1266.
- Marino, R. and Tomei, P. (1999). An adaptive output feedback control for a class of nonlinear systems with time-varying parameters. *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, 44(11), 2190–2194.
- Marino, R. and Tomei, P. (2003). Adaptive control of linear time-varying systems. *Automatica*, 39(4), 651–659.
- Middleton, R.H. and Goodwin, G.C. (1988). Adaptive control of time-varying linear systems. *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, 33(2), 150–155.
- Narendra, K.S. and Annaswamy, A.M. (1989). *Stable Adaptive Systems*. Prentice Hall.
- Nestruiev, J. (2020). *Smooth Manifolds and Observables*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2 edition.
- Patil, O.S., Sun, R., Bhasin, S., and Dixon, W.E. (2022). Adaptive control of time-varying parameter systems with asymptotic tracking. *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*.
- Tao, G. (2003). *Adaptive Control Design and Analysis*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Tsakalis, K. and Ioannou, P.A. (1987). Adaptive control of linear time-varying plants. *Automatica*, 23(4), 459–468.
- Wang, C. and Guo, L. (2017). Adaptive cooperative tracking control for a class of nonlinear time-varying multi-agent systems. *J. of the Franklin Inst.*, 354(15), 6766–6782.
- Wang, J., Hovakimyan, N., and Cao, C. (2009). \mathcal{L}_1 adaptive augmentation of gain-scheduled controller for race-track maneuver in aerial refueling. In *Guid. Navigation and Control Conf.*, 5739. AIAA.
- Zhang, Z., Xie, X.J., and Ge, S.S. (2019). Adaptive tracking for uncertain MIMO nonlinear systems with time-varying parameters and bounded disturbance. *IEEE Trans. Syst., Man, Cybern.*